

CoreTrustSeal: Specialists, Generalists, and Repository & Data Service Providers

Final Report. A response to community feedback

Executive Summary	1
Overview	2
High-level Feedback to the Consultation	5
Machine Actionability	5
Curation/Preservation Investment	6
Interdisciplinary/Cross-Disciplinary Research	6
Software vs Technical vs other Repository Data Service Providers	6
CoreTrustSeal Remit	6
Support	7
Specific Per Requirement Feedback	7
R0. Context	7
R0. Repository type	7
R0. Brief Description of Repository	7
R0. Designated Community	8
R0. Level of Curation	8
R0. Context. Insource/Outsource Partners.	9
R1. Mission	9
R2. Licenses	10
R3. Continuity of Access	10
R4. Confidentiality and Ethics	11
R5. Organizational Infrastructure	12
R6. Expert Guidance	12
R7. Integrity and Authenticity	13
R8. Appraisal	14
R9. Documented Storage Procedures	14
R10. Preservation Plan	14
R11. Data quality	15
R12. Workflows	16
R13. Data discovery and identification	17
R14. Data reuse	17
R15. Technical infrastructure	18
R16. Security	19

Executive Summary

The CoreTrustSeal¹ Board solicited feedback on issues around certification scope, generalist and specialist Trustworthy Data Repositories (TDRs), and repository and data services providers. We would like to thank the community for their extensive, detailed, engaged, and informed recommendations. The results of this process will inform future consultations, the next revision of the CoreTrustSeal, and an evolving consultation on the strategic priorities of the CoreTrustSeal.

To support the research community recommendation that data be deposited in disciplinary TDRs, the CoreTrustSeal Board will ask each applicant whether they self-identify as a specialist repository, and to state which disciplines or domains they serve. This information should be recorded in an appropriate repository registry. The CoreTrustSeal will expect more explicit evidence in line with any specialist status, but will continue to be a domain/discipline agnostic certification that is open to generalist and specialist repositories. We will consult on clearer differentiation between these curation levels and contribute to the development of metadata that supports discovery of each repository type. The CoreTrustSeal Board will actively support efforts to build more granular specifications around the 'core' requirements.

The CoreTrustSeal 'TDR' status will be open only to those organisations actively curating data for long-term preservation. An applicant may seek external expertise in preservation or outsource preservation actions, but it must retain the rights and responsibilities over why, how, and when preservation actions are taken on data and metadata to ensure that digital objects remain accessible and usable in the face of changes to technology, community practices, or other needs of its Designated Community.

The CoreTrustSeal will actively engage with the community of technical repository service providers to identify which types of services could be defined as 'CoreTrustSeal-Ready' in a future extension to the core certification model.

All of the Requirement-specific feedback received will be integrated into the next review of the CoreTrustSeal. The Board will consult on and document the range of strategic challenges faced by the data management, curation, and preservation community. Any proposed amendments or extensions to the scope of the CoreTrustSeal certification will be subject to community consultation. Outcomes of work on strategic priorities will then be reflected in a revised CoreTrustSeal business model to ensure continued transparency, sustainability, and scalability of the standard and certification services that are offered.

¹ For the current version of the CoreTrustSeal TDR Requirements, please refer to <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3638211>.

Overview

The vision of CoreTrustSeal is to set standards and deliver assessments that enable repositories to be certified as capable of fulfilling a mission to provide a level of appraisal and curation that supports continued access through active preservation of digital objects.

Preservation requires that such digital objects (data, metadata, and documentation) remain usable for a Designated Community of users; specifically, that the objects can be understood for their intended purpose and that users can interact with them in ways meeting their objectives, as well as their intellectual, technological, and process needs.

Standards that seek to establish TDR status^{2 3 4} share the Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System (OAIS)⁵ as a common reference point for identifying mandatory responsibilities.

Diagram: A simplified overview of mandatory OAIS responsibilities

The CoreTrustSeal could notionally offer standards and assessments that fall short of these responsibilities, or define standards and assessments that go far beyond them. However, in either case, it would be inappropriate to misuse the label 'Trustworthy Digital Repository' outside its intended meaning and scope.

This paper is the final report from the internal working group tasked with responding to requests from a number of stakeholders. It seeks to clarify and address the needs of the domain/subject-based repository community while meeting the demand for assessment, peer review, and recognition from a wider group of actors who deliver data curation, storage, and access services. These stakeholders include a number of more generalist repositories

² [CoreTrustSeal](#)

³ [nestor Seal for Trustworthy Digital Archives](#)

⁴ [ISO16363 audit and certification of Trustworthy Digital Repositories](#)

⁵ [Reference Model for an Open Archival Information System \(OAIS\)](#)

and organizations that provide technical infrastructure and other data services to repositories.

This report presents the initial results of a number of community engagements and requests for comment that will feed into the next formal review of CoreTrustSeal in 2022. It is released as a revised version, incorporating feedback received from comments, of the original consultation document⁶. Our goals are to provide clarity on the eligibility of who can apply for the current CoreTrustSeal certification and to identify how we can support the other critical actors involved in the future.

Policy makers including Science Europe recommend deposit in disciplinary repositories⁷. In response to the need for certification of repositories, beyond these specialist (domain/subject-based) curation providers, which formed the majority of previous applicant repositories, the CoreTrustSeal also recognises the need for generalist curation. Such recognition also acknowledges that resources do not permit all data to be curated to the same level. Generalist repositories provide essential services for governmental, cultural, and scientific data, including critical contributions to data management in galleries, archives, libraries and museums.

Applicant: CoreTrustSeal status is attached to an applicant with direct responsibility for the curation and preservation of their collection objects' data and metadata. This is reflected in the following draft statement on 'Who can apply':

“An official representative acting on behalf of an organisation whose mission includes the curation and long-term preservation of a specified data collection; specifically, the provision of the appropriate infrastructure (documented policies, people and skills, workflows, and technologies) to preserve data, such that they remain accessible and reusable over time. To fulfil this mission, the organisation must have sufficient expertise and management rights over the data to respond to changes in the technologies and the knowledge base of a well-defined Designated Community of users. The applicant may outsource to third parties. Outsourcing roles and relationships should be well defined. All parties must provide evidence related to responsibilities for all of the functions or processes that they help undertake.”

In future, we propose to define each successful CoreTrustSeal applicant as either representing a specialist (e.g., domain or subject-based) or a generalist repository. Between now and the next revision of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements, we will consult with the community on whether these two repository types (providing different curation levels) need to be more clearly differentiated through logos, badging, or some other means. We will also cooperate with repository registries to ensure appropriate organisational metadata are made available to those seeking specific, specialist TDRs.

Specialist Repositories: The key recommendation from many data policymakers is that the value of data assets is maximised for the long term if they are deposited in a domain or subject-based repository ([Glossary](#)). Such repositories must ensure that their stated area of expertise is evidenced in terms of meeting specialist (e.g. domain, disciplinary) standards as required by their Designated Community. They must have the skills and the processes to

⁶ CoreTrustSeal: Specialists, Generalists, and Technical Repository Service Providers

⁷ https://www.scienceeurope.org/media/jezkhnoo/se_rdm_practical_guide_final.pdf

support the data, the depositors and the end users within that community. They can be multi-specialist (e.g., multidisciplinary), but this is not the same as 'discipline agnostic'. A specialist repository may also offer generalist repository services. Generalist repository requirements are a subset of those applied to specialist repositories.

Generalist Repositories: With a potentially heterogeneous collection, and one or more non-specialist user communities, generalist repositories provide a critical curation and preservation role for many data assets. Generalists can claim a broader (including public) Designated Community, and may therefore set more general expectations for formats, metadata, and other standards. Generalist repositories may not be expected to provide the types of granular metadata, data discovery, or support that would be expected from a specialist repository. They are expected, however, to have considered and defined the knowledge base of their Designated Community, along with the capabilities that are needed to support that community.

The existing CoreTrustSeal Requirements and evidence expectations will be elaborated or extended to enable the assessment process to differentiate more clearly between:

- A specialist repository serving a defined Designated Community including a clear disciplinary, domain or subjects-based knowledge base.
- A generalist repository serving a broader Designated Community with a less specialised knowledge base.

Technical Repository Service Providers (TRSP): Software providers and providers of technical infrastructure and associated data services that support TDRs are vital components of the data ecosystem. These tools and services do not accept direct responsibility for the selection, curation, appraisal, and access conditions of the data they hold on a temporary or permanent basis. Similar to an insource/outsource provider, TRSPs need to offer evidence for the functions and activities that they support. The informal TRSP abbreviation is used below for brevity, but it is acknowledged that it covers a wide range of possible types of services that need to be clarified and supported.

In parallel to revisions of its TDR Requirements, CoreTrustSeal will engage with the providers of products and services that either directly provide technical systems for repositories, or otherwise provide partnership and support. Such actors have always been a critical part of the data ecosystem, but we need to address applications for certification that depend on increasingly co-dependent partnerships including:

- Other insource/outsource partners supporting various repository functions and activities with their services.
- Software or other products used by repositories without a specific partnership relationship.

A number of contributors pointed out that the relationship between a repository and a TRSP outsource partner should be regulated by a contract, Memorandum of Understanding (MoU), Service Level Agreement (SLA) or similar agreement, and that the respective document should be provided as evidence to make transparent the agreements between the repository and the third party. Contributors suggested that the following aspects should be addressed in such a contract, MoU or SLA:

- the service content to be provided by the third party, including the technical indicators, service response, service period, responsibilities and obligations of both parties, such as confidentiality terms, etc.;
- Information on how the SLA will be implemented by the partners, including a clear assignment of roles and responsibilities;
- Clear documentation on how the two entities interact, in terms of data exchange.

This discussion on the types and roles of repository and data service actors is timely as large-scale infrastructure efforts, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), seek to identify the expectations of partnership services in a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) context. There is already acknowledgement that FAIR needs a preservation element to provide stability and sustainability over time. The F, A, and R of FAIR are closely aligned with the CoreTrustSeal Requirements. A TDR addresses interoperability through meeting the needs of its data depositors and user communities, but the detailed scope of interoperability within large scale data infrastructure remains to be defined.

This working group report from CoreTrustSeal starts to address the assessment criteria necessary to provide trustworthy, stable, and scalable repository data services in an increasingly co-dependent and partnership-driven world. This also relies on increased transparency through the provision of public, online evidence. As partnerships, dependencies, and interoperability requirements become more complex, it is impractical to express all the relevant evidence within a CoreTrustSeal application. Transparent, public, online evidence is always to be preferred.

High-level Feedback to the Consultation

This section describes some of the broader issues raised by this consultation while the following sections provide issues raised per-requirement. We must identify how these can best be addressed. This might be through clearly implied changes to the next revision of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements, or it may depend on additional discussion within the CoreTrustSeal Community. In other cases, broader community consensus will be necessary before we can identify clear and consistent next steps. The CoreTrustSeal Board will lead where possible and cooperate more widely as necessary. There were also valid and important items of feedback whose scope is not appropriate for a 'core' requirement set that is seeking to maintain a low barrier to entry for applicants.

Machine Actionability

Feedback included a suggestion about grouping CoreTrustSeal criteria by whether they can be evaluated automatically through *some* generic system, whether they require non-expert human input, or whether a more specialised human or machine agent is required. The Board supports all measures to automate assessment, but notes that this depends on community-agreed standards and tools at both the general and the specialist levels.

Curation/Preservation Investment

Some recommendations noted that the investment necessary to curate and preserve data increases with the level of data complexity and/or the specialism of the Designated Community. The Board acknowledges this resource issue, and it seeks to define a tiered approach from bit-level assurance, through to general and then specialised curation. The Appraisal Requirement (R8) covers the need to assess data for deposit into a repository, but CoreTrustSeal does not seek to assess the value of data or define which level of curation they should receive. The Board, however, does believe that the levels of data curation and preservation applied to data and metadata should be transparent, as should any change in the level of care over time.

Interdisciplinary/Cross-Disciplinary Research

A number of recommendations noted that research is increasingly interdisciplinary and cross-disciplinary. The Board recognises, and seeks to clarify, the difference between a generalist repository and a repository that provides support for one or more disciplines. A generalist repository containing data from many domains is not the same as a domain(s)-specific repository that serves transdisciplinary research. To avoid silos, a specialist repository should be open to expanding its support to serve multi-disciplinary needs.

Software vs Technical vs other Repository Data Service Providers

The original consultation text differentiated generalists/specialist repositories (with explicit curation and preservation responsibility) from 'technical' repository service providers that might support these applicants. Feedback has made it clear that not all support services are necessarily 'technical' and that within technical services, there is a clear distinction between provision of services and provision of software. Feedback focussed more on the assessment of services than software. The Board is considering the broad range of external actors that support applicants by providing relevant evidence about products or services.

The Board does not see broad consensus on the certification of software, but will seek to cooperate with vendors who are trying to support their customers. This could include clearly documented software functionality that is matched with a list of common repository actions.

Though feedback did not demonstrate an appetite for a separate formal certification of TRSP, there is a desire for clarity on how third parties might offer supporting services and how receiving such services would affect the certification of repositories. This might be achieved through community consensus on a standard set of functions and actions that cover these services, which is then supported by specific guidance on what evidence might support their clients' CoreTrustSeal applications. This in turn could evolve into the assessment of some third parties as 'CoreTrustSeal Ready' for a specific set of functions.

CoreTrustSeal Remit

One recommendation in support of generalist repository certification noted that "CTS certification should not be about, if a repository is the right one for a given dataset". This may

be beyond the CoreTrustSeal remit, but we will always seek to act in a way that supports depositors and users in finding the most capable repository to support their needs.

Support

Several recommendations included the need for trustworthy digital repository support to depositors and users. A clear expectation of support for depositors (as opposed to an 'untended' self-deposit and access process) might be a valid addition to CoreTrustSeal. Evidence for support from specialist repositories would need to include expertise in their stated domain. Inclusion of depositor and user support as a basic 'core' requirement is a candidate for future revisions of the CoreTrustSeal.

Specific per Requirement Feedback

In the sections below, we address the feedback to consultation on particular CoreTrustSeal Requirements. Orange

R0. Context

R0. Repository type

"Repository Type. Select all relevant types from:

- Domain or subject-based repository
- Institutional repository
- National repository system, including governmental
- Publication repository
- Library
- Museum
- Archive
- Research project repository
- Other (Please describe)"

Despite some agreement with the current list, a number of people note that it mixes different classes in the same list and that these should be split out. An 'institutional repository', for example, could be a specialist or a generalist repository, or a self-deposit TRSP. There was no consensus on how this should be done. 'Publication' and 'Research Project Repository' were both flagged as potentially unclear. A number of contributors noted that TRSP did not fit into this classification and should have a separate list.

CoreTrustSeal will review this list for future versions of the Requirements but will also seek wider community consensus of typologies for repositories that are mapped to clear user expectations about service delivery.

R0. Brief Description of Repository

The consultation asked whether we need to ask more specific questions about the digital objects and collections being curated under context and which object or collection characteristics are most relevant to an assessment. The recommendations made it clear that there was a demand for clearer typologies of data in repository collections, and more clarity

on any different levels of curation applied within the data collections being curated. The CoreTrustSeal is committed to making progress here, but clear typologies are complicated and hard to agree. The Board would like to see some common data type and collection profile ontologies emerge from the data management community.

R0. Designated Community

A generalist repository may serve a broader designated community of users. A specialist repository must define the knowledge base of their community more specifically. All applicants must demonstrate clear interaction with and responsiveness to their primary designated communities.

Though some contributors seemed less familiar with the designated community concept, there were no suggestions for alternate approaches to identifying the 'customer' expectations that a repository should meet over time. The Board will consider additional guidance and exemplars on the Designated Community topic. The Board would like to see community discussion on any minimum level of evidence that repositories should provide to support their designated community self-assessment statements.

R0. Level of Curation

- A. Content distributed as deposited
- B. Basic curation – e.g., brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation
- C. Enhanced curation – e.g., conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation
- D. Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data for accuracy

In general, the contributors tended to agree that the curation levels meet the needs of both specialist and generalist repositories as the focus is on the approach to curation, not about the type of repository. However, the definitions could benefit from review; especially the distinction between C and D seemed unclear. If more than one level is selected, it might be necessary to clarify what parts of the collection each approach addresses.

A higher level of formal provenance, integrity, and version management (change logs, etc.) is expected as curation levels progress from A through to D.

There was some concern about level D curation and editing of data. Some contributors make a general assumption that the separation of data and metadata can always be clear, or that metadata changes are always acceptable and data changes are not. Repositories in fact play a large number of more and less active roles in the data journey and the CoreTrustSeal must support all of these types. Any level of curation will usually depend on copies rather than originals; rights and provenance are the key to understanding the actions taken. A best practice recommendation would be that the scope of any data changes to be made by the repository should be clearly agreed upon with the data depositor and clearly communicated to data users.

The CoreTrustSeal will follow up on suggestions about alignment with criteria including the NDSA levels of preservation regarding metadata and content curation. The Board would also like to see community discussion about how best to describe and communicate information

about heterogeneous collections (in terms of both digital object types and curation approaches). A standard way of describing 'collection profiles' would support repositories and their stakeholders as well as the assessment process.

R0. Context. Insource/Outsource Partners.

If a specialist or generalist repository shares some part of their work with a third party, how should we best identify exactly where the partner takes responsibility? Is evidence per requirement sufficient, or should this R0 section provide a mapping by function, or activity areas, or by some other means?

Function: e.g. deposit (R8), curation (R11), storage (R9), preservation (R10), discovery (R13) access/use (R14).

Activity Area: e.g. rights management (R2), continuity of access (R3), integrity checks and authenticity measure (R7), workflow management (R12), identifier management (R13), technical infrastructure management (R15), security management (R16).

Some contributors felt the current approach was sufficient but a number were in favour of designing and applying a mapping to support this contextual information and other requirements (e.g. R3, Continuity) where clarifying the specific roles a partner played was important. The CoreTrustSeal will consider approaches to defining a framework of functions that supports applicants in mapping activities to insource/outsource. Ideally, this would align with a broader based (e.g. full lifecycle) community consensus to allow flexibility and additions from applicants (data analytics was mentioned as an example).

This approach has the potential for clarifying the roles of third party repository and data service providers in a way that supports their classification as 'CoreTrustSeal-ready' for specific functions or activity areas.

R1. Mission

An applicant must have a mission that delivers long-term access to data and metadata including the provision of active preservation. Both specialist and generalist repositories should have a clear and comparable mission.

Contributors were less certain over the need for mission information from a supporting repository and data service provider and focussed more on their meeting the defined and contracted needs of their clients. Contributors prioritised TRSP sustainability over the period of certification (R3).

At least one contributor was not clear on the implications of active preservation, a critical concept that the Board will seek to further clarify and communicate. The CoreTrustSeal Board will also seek to define and set boundaries around the expectation of the Mission and consider whether there is a need for a clearer set of data types, collection profiles, and mapping of activities in R0. Context could replace some of the prose questions under R1. Clearer context questions to confirm that the applicant is taking responsibility for active preservation at generalist or specialist levels would provide assurance that the application was in scope and could simplify the review process.

R2. Licenses

The applicant must be responsible for assuring that the licences agreed at appraisal (R8) are sufficient for the level of curation quality and preservation of the data, and for the permissions, prohibitions, and duties applicable to data users. Both generalist and specialist repositories should provide, via public licences or other routes, a statement describing the rights and responsibilities that are associated with each digital object.

There was broad support that evidence expectations for licences should be similar for both specialist and generalist repositories and that these must be the responsibility of the applicant repository rather than any third party. There was clear support for open and standard licences where possible, but there was an acknowledged need for more specialised licences for more complex data or situations (e.g. access to sensitive data). While the CoreTrustSeal can point applicants to best practices around selecting licences, the setting of a controlled list of permitted licences is beyond the scope of CoreTrustSeal.

Several contributors noted the need for both generalist and specialist repositories to provide advice for depositors to understand the implications of the licenses to be applied to deposited data and to users for understanding the implications of data licenses (see “Support” above). It was clear from feedback that all repositories should clarify the depositors’ rights to sign agreements and to specify or approve rights conferred to the repository and end users. For any terms or conditions that have expiration dates, both generalist and specialist repositories must specify the actions that will be taken upon expiration or enact mechanisms to renew or replace such terms or conditions.

All repositories and all data service providers should make it clear whether sensitive information, including any personally identifiable information or other information that is confidential, private, or protected by laws, statutes, or other legal means can be deposited. They should specify any conditions under which such information must be protected for curation, storage and access.

The scope of the feedback implies that revisions to R2 should be considered to more broadly cover ‘rights management’ at the next CoreTrustSeal revision.

R3. Continuity of Access

Continuity of access includes the applicant's ability to ensure business continuity, disaster recovery, and succession planning. Dependencies on any third party should form part of any continuity risk management. Additional risks might include the potential outcomes of non-payment to a third party service provider, or the lack of a data portability solution if a provider ceases to offer the service.

It was considered that for specialist repositories with more complex workflows and a larger reliance on specific expertise, the recovery to full service from a major incident could be more challenging.

One contributor asked whether there should be more ‘leeway’ for generalist repositories which may support a wider range of formats and data types. The Board considers that this kind of challenge or risk applies to generalist repositories more broadly than for R3. Some suggested that other factors, such as differences in data volumes, hardware costs, or data portability would be more significant factors to continuity of access than repository type.

It was suggested that the desired level of disaster recovery provision might depend on how 'critical' the data and services were. Defining this criticality is beyond the remit of CoreTrustSeal, which must instead focus on whether the approach and supporting evidence meets the stated designated community needs.

The consultation asked what additional evidence an applicant should provide on behalf of a TRSP or other third party that they rely upon. Is a contract or memorandum of understanding sufficient, or do we need to know more about the service providers own approach to risk?

There was some debate on whether an SLA/Contract with a TRSP would be enough evidence or if the TRSP should present their own business continuity evidence. This might depend on which functions the TRSP supports and the degree to which the functions represent a 'single point of failure' in repository service delivery. Some contributors suggested TRSP (especially large providers) would be less transparent or unduly engaged with providing evidence. Several suggested that mitigating risk should include a clear data and service exit strategy from any single TRSP.

The CoreTrustSeal Board concurs that Business Continuity, Disaster Recovery, and Succession Planning are organisational factors that apply across all data storage and curation organisations. Evidence expectations should be broadly consistent across all applicants, but there are clear challenges in expecting evidence to be provided from a potentially large list of third party service providers (that may in turn use other third parties). The Board would like to see wider discussion and consensus on how the community should define and evidence complex relationships and minimise risks to data and services.

It was agreed that minimum levels of bit assurance should be the same for all actors, though this might be better addressed under R7. Integrity & Authenticity.

R4. Confidentiality and Ethics

It was agreed that confidentiality and ethics expectations should reach the same minimum level for both generalist and specialist repositories, though specialists may need to meet more specific domain expectations. It was suggested that the lower level of curation from generalists meant they were less responsible for ethical issues and had a greater need to depend on ethical committees and clear statements from depositors at the point of appraisal.

There was not clear consensus on whether a TRSP should offer an ethics statement in addition to any service level agreement provided, but this may be due to a lack of specificity in the question as it is acknowledged that a wide range of services and roles could be delivered by a TRSP.

It was agreed that overall standards remained the responsibility of the repository applicant. In feedback, there was some conflation of issues around legislation (e.g. GDPR), general academic ethics practices, and specific measures necessary to handle more sensitive data types (personal, commercial or others with a risk associated with disclosure). Future revisions to the requirements might more explicitly separate awareness of the general legislative environment from basic academic compliance and wider awareness of privacy issues. This requirement also focuses on the handling of sensitive data, which may lead to some confusion for repositories that do not offer this type of data.

The CoreTrustSeal needs to seek evidence of awareness about relevant issues and statements of compliance while avoiding any suggestion that it is conferring formal legal or ethical approval. It may also be beneficial to highlight that the CoreTrustSeal scope applies to the data within collections and not to the wider responsibility for legal and ethical handling of repository staff or users' information.

As noted under R2, all repositories and all data service providers should make it clear whether sensitive information, including any personally identifiable information, or any information that is confidential, private, or protected by laws, statutes, or other legal means can be deposited. They should specify any conditions under which such information must be protected for curation, storage and access, as well as having procedures in place for the event that such information is accidentally submitted, e.g. via an online form.

Though there is a need to further define ethical expectations and to provide a clearer separation between legal and ethical aspects, there is broad acceptance that this requirement applies to all repository types and that handling sensitive data increases the expectations for demonstrating good practice and providing supporting evidence.

R5. Organizational Infrastructure

Understanding the organisational structure, governance, and the availability of appropriately skilled resources is invaluable in the assessment process and applies to all the organisations involved. Specialist repositories are expected to demonstrate the skills applicable to the stated domain, discipline, or subject area of their designated community.

It is considered ideal if, as for repositories, TRSP organisational infrastructure information is publicly available including, governance, funding, adequate personnel, and clear provisions for shared expertise across organisations. Feedback indicated some concerns that a TRSP might be less transparent than a repository or simply too big a player to share information needed for assessment. This was considered to be another case that depends on how TRSP services match repository functions, and the degree to which they are a single point of failure. It was also noted that suppliers in turn have their own supply chains and there is a limited degree to which we can expect all of them to provide recursive organisational infrastructure details. On the other hand, there was concern that CoreTrustSeal might certify a repository that relied heavily on TRSP partners that were insufficiently transparent.

Ultimately, it remains the applicant repositories' responsibility to choose their partners, explain the relationship (including contractual), manage the related risk, and develop appropriate contingency plans or an exit scenario.

R6. Expert Guidance

The expert guidance to be demonstrated under R6 is mainly focussed on the applicant seeking appropriate external scientific and technical knowledge through wider engagement. This would apply equally to a specialist or generalist repository in line with the curation levels offered. A TRSP may provide some aspects of this expert guidance and could therefore provide supporting evidence.

The broad theme of the recommendations seems to be that for a TRSP, the contract with the repository and the supporting evidence provided are more important than demonstrating access to external experts. The TRSP's service provision should be clear and well

demonstrated through contracts and evidence including statistics, user feedback and standards compliance.

R7. Integrity and Authenticity

An actor in any part of the data lifecycle with storage (see also R9) responsibility for data should be able to demonstrate integrity measures that ensure unintended change is monitored and mitigated. It would be beneficial for the community of practice to identify minimum and ideal levels of data integrity assurance that could be applied equally to a specialist, a generalist, or a TRSP.

For the repository phase of the lifecycle, assuring data integrity may become more challenging for higher curation levels i.e. the more intended changes made to data or metadata. Higher levels of curation also imply a need for more detailed records of change to support authenticity.

Though the ideal level of provenance may depend on the demands of the designated community, it would be beneficial for the community to reach consensus on minimal provenance expectations. Increasing the level of pre-deposit authenticity information to maximise data provenance is also desirable.

A CoreTrustSeal applicant must retain responsibility for the integrity and provenance measures that are applied to data under curation, even if mediated by a TRSP. This should be covered by the contractual agreement between the TRSP and the repository. Some feedback indicated varying underlying assumptions about what a TRSP does and does not do on behalf of a repository, from basic storage at one extreme to providing systems that mediate every curation step at the other. This again implies a need for matching outsource providers to some common functions or actions.

Minimal expectations for ensuring integrity and auditing intended changes should be similar across generalists, specialists and their TRSP. The repository would be expected to provide more detailed input on the intellectual side of managing and recording intended changes.

Capturing a clear provenance audit trail at both the metadata and data level is clearly desirable. There was some doubt over whether we could reach community consensus on minimum expectations for provenance, with one contributor noting the challenges of extending provenance to distributed environments across the lifecycle. Some suggested that we should seek to agree on minimal actions, including checks for authenticity at the point of deposit and measures taken during curation and preservation.

The consensus indicated that the challenge of managing integrity and recording provenance might be greater for specialist repositories generating more numerous changes to data and metadata, but that the overall evidence outcomes should be comparable.

The recommendations make it clear that the division of work between repository and TRSP has to be clearly agreed upon, and appropriate contracts and control mechanisms need to be in place.

Some recommendations highlighted that CoreTrustSeal should make a distinction between aspects that can be verified automatically and aspects that need to be verified by a human (See 'Machine Actionability' under high-level feedback above). This will be considered in the

next review of the CoreTrustSeal Requirements alongside alignment with other community criteria (e.g. NDSA⁸, Preservation Storage Criteria⁹).

R8. Appraisal

Demonstrating a clear collection development plan, including an appraisal process that supports the definition of clear curation and preservation actions, must remain the responsibility of the applicant. A TRSP may offer evidence that it supports these measures.

One contributor noted that in OAIS terms, 'appraisal' is part of Ingest, but from a CoreTrustSeal perspective, appraisal is a key stage as the 'gatekeeper' for data and metadata entering the repository. Appraisal was considered "crucial & complex", but it seems that evidence outcomes should be similar across specialists and generalists except for any additional criteria applied by the specialist repository. There remains a level of overlap between evidence for appraisal, quality (R11) and re-use (R14) that the CoreTrustSeal Board will review at the next revision of the requirements.

R9. Documented Storage Procedures

Documented storage procedures in R9 are addressed from the perspective of active deposit, curation, and preservation measures, in contrast to the wider application of a technical infrastructure covered under R16.

Any specialist or generalist repository must document any storage procedures where they have control of the storage. Where they rely partially or completely on an TRSP to provide storage, the provider may provide supporting evidence. The expectation of detailed evidence will increase for higher levels of curation.

Some contributors questioned this mix of storage and curation evidence under 'digital object management' while another noted that repositories need to store data and metadata from the point of deposit, through the ingest process, to the point of access, as well as in archival storage systems. The more changes a repository makes, the larger the number of commitments to storage systems. Evidence statements should make it clear what level of risk is in place and how this is mitigated: back up periodicity, maximum period of possible data loss etc.

The consensus is that, overall, the documentation of storage practice should apply equally to generalists, specialists or TRSP. There may be a need for CoreTrustSeal to communicate that evidence must be provided for data 'in motion' through the repository as well as that 'at rest' in archival storage. At the next review, the CoreTrustSeal Board will also consider whether this requirement should be integrated into R15, Technical Infrastructure, along with some more specific questions about each stage of repository storage.

R10. Preservation Plan

The applicant must take responsibility for an active preservation plan covering data and metadata in line with the expectations of the designated community. A generalist repository may accept a wider range of formats and curate less detailed metadata than a specialist

⁸ <https://ndsa.org/publications/levels-of-digital-preservation/>

⁹ <https://osf.io/sjc6u/>

repository. Preservation actions may be outsourced to a TRSP, but preservation plans and decisions may not.

The CoreTrustSeal acknowledges that academic recommendations usually focus on the need to deposit in a domain or subject-based repository. We support this and recognise that specialist data in non-specialist repositories may receive a less specialised level of curation. However, it is not the role of the CoreTrustSeal to make judgements about whether data is in the “right place” during the application process, only to evaluate whether the declared needs of the designated community are being met.

The statement “*Bit-level ‘preservation’ is important, but not sufficient*” was seen as critical to communicating the real range of preservation actions needed. It was considered that in general the evidence for specialists and generalists would be similar. One contributor noted that “*formats are just formats*” but it is important to acknowledge that specialist or proprietary file formats and supporting environments may be more volatile, resource-intensive, or less supported than more popular and generally available formats. There is a risk that generalist repositories will not have capacity to preserve the breadth of formats that they accept. Specialist repositories will be expected to demonstrate that they maintain formats (or offer emulation etc.) and semantics that meet the detailed needs of their designated communities in addition to more generally applicable data and metadata formats.

It was acknowledged that ongoing understandability and potential for reusability by the designated community depends on repository actions to update context, documentation, and metadata over time. Specialist repositories must demonstrate that they can perform this service for their stated domain(s) of expertise. Conceivably, all technical aspects of preservation (format migration, bit level integrity, tiered retrieval) could be provided and verified by a TRSP. However, throughout the process, the responsibility for defining and applying technical and intellectual updates remains the responsibility of the applicant repository.

Contributors considered it acceptable to certify both generalist and specialist repositories as long as these differences in curation and preservation practices “*are made transparent to the stakeholders – by logos/badging*” etc.

Even in this self-selecting group of contributors, the variations in the level of understanding about what preservation requires was wide. The CoreTrustSeal needs to more clearly define and present their expectations for active preservation, ideally through broad consensus with the wider data management community.

R11. Data quality

The “scientific” quality of data is for funders, depositors, and users to evaluate. A trustworthy digital repository ensures the technical quality and understandability of data through curation actions that ensure standards compliance and meet the needs of the designated community.

These actions start to be defined at appraisal (R8), are implemented at R11, and communicated at the point of data re-use (R14). The applicant may outsource actions to ensure data and metadata quality, but must take responsibility for defining those actions. A TRSP should provide evidence that actions have been implemented.

The consultation asked whether the community could reach consensus on the minimal practice for data and metadata curation and preservation (for appraisal, curation quality and re-use) that is acceptable from a generalist repository. Is this a key differentiator between a generalist repository and a TRSP?

While some contributors wondered whether consensus was possible, or even desirable, the general expectation was that “*The community should reach a consensus on the minimal practice for data and metadata curation and preservation*”, with examples including [PREMIS](#) for preservation metadata standard. However, the recommendations reflected perceived limits on what was practical.

We can objectively measure some technical aspects of quality and consider levels of standards compliance, but ensuring data is understandable requires documentation and context that usually requires some human intervention. This role is considered to be a key differentiator between a generalist repository that defines and applies general quality criteria to data and metadata, and a TRSP that is mechanistically focussing on metadata field completeness and assurance that bit-streams remain unaltered.

For a specialist repository the additional challenge is to ensure a degree of semantic quality that meets the needs of their specialist data users across data and metadata, including controlled vocabularies and ontologies. A specialist repository needs to have processes in place to negotiate and interact with the depositors to ensure the quality control of the digital objects. Repositories should ideally provide a mechanism to allow users' to provide feedback on perceived data quality.

Further definitions of the differences between technical and scientific quality, and a clear community consensus on minimum quality evaluations would benefit the community, although one contributor noted that implementation of these measures would need to be very slow and gradual, as the repository practice could only be developed through cooperation within the framework of discipline-specific pilots.

R12. Workflows

All specialist, generalist, and TRSP must document the workflows that they undertake. Overall responsibility for ensuring that workflows are fit for the mission and meet the needs of the designated community remain with the applicant. Specialist repositories should highlight workflow items that are particular to their discipline or domain.

Contributors generally agreed that responsibility for the approval of workflows (if not the day-to-day implementation) must reside with the repository applicant and that this is a key differentiator from a TRSP. The repository must ensure that workflow processes and supporting documentation are comprehensive and account for all phases of the data lifecycle in which the repository is involved.

Contributors indicated that a documented common understanding of workflows was important when working with a TRSP to define actions and to make lock-in less likely. Workflows are considered essential for appraisal across the lifecycle alongside clearly defined standards. There should be evidence that workflows are reviewed and revised, to address evolution in technologies and standards, identified deficiencies, and scope changes. One contributor suggested that workflows should be “documented, publicly available, and

metrics generated to determine compliance”. Workflows are a clear candidate for community consensus on minimum expectations at the core level.

R13. Data discovery and identification

Defining and achieving standards for discovery and persistent identification must remain the responsibility of the applicant. All repositories must ensure persistent identification and enable general searching locally or through third parties. In addition, specialist repositories must address the more specific resource discovery needs of their designated communities. A TRSP can provide supporting evidence when identification and discovery use their systems.

Standardised persistent identifiers and resource discovery systems are generally agreed to be key to data sharing and there was broad agreement with the statements in the consultation document. Some contributors highlighted the need for local discovery systems while others noted that local search may not be necessary if there were standard interfaces and search engines established for use by a community. In these cases, the TRSP or other third parties that provide this centralised discovery would be described in evidence statements.

Overall, specialist search would be expected to support specialist collections. All identification and search should be demonstrably in line with the needs of the designated community.

R14. Data reuse

The quantity and complexity of metadata required to enable access and re-use in line with the stated mission may be lower for a generalist than a specialist repository. But in all cases, it remains the applicant who must identify the needs of their designated community and demonstrate that those needs are met. Interactions with users, including collection of usage statistics and feedback, may be mediated through a TRSP.

The recommendations indicated agreement with the consultation statement, including the benefits of mapping outsourced functions to TRSP so that the applicant can demonstrate that they seek feedback on outsourced user-facing systems.

One contributor suggested that re-use was “*largely dependent on appropriate licenses, metadata, and provenance with special cases for controlled access data*” while another noted that a “*generalist repository using standardized metadata formats, may actually make data more reusable by other communities by forcing them into a generic shared data model whereas a domain specific repository may only make it reusable for their designated community*”. In the CoreTrustSeal experience, disciplinary and other specialist repositories provide formats and metadata standards for both a general audience and to standards that meet the more specific needs of their designated community. In future versions of the requirements, the Board will seek to highlight that specialist repository measures should be taken in addition to more generalist curation practice and not instead of it.

One item of feedback stated that “*more specific reference to which metadata standards are in place is needed (e.g. discovery vs reuse) and management of new versions of standards. Use of local standards should be supported by evidence of responsiveness to community needs. With tracking, statistical and evaluative work on data reuse [and] records and*

statistics of user access and data downloading. A repository should assess the data reuse effectiveness and efficiency, which will be an important input of the repository's future development plan."

The CoreTrustSeal will consider both a more specific request for a list of standards in use, and seek further community input on what evidence of engagement with and responsiveness to a designated community is required for generalist or specialist repositories. Reaching community consensus on minimal and ideal measures that ensure users' needs are met is critical to service delivery and improvement.

R15. Technical infrastructure

Many recommendations implied that provision of technical infrastructure is seen as the primary role of a TRSP, though the CoreTrustSeal Board is keen to identify and support a wider range of service providers. As outsourcing elements of technical infrastructure becomes more common, applicants will depend more on providers for supporting evidence. However, the applicant remains responsible for defining the expectations of the technical infrastructure and the relationship with any outsource partners.

One contributor noted *"repositories need to operate on reliable and stable core infrastructures that maximizes service availability. Furthermore, hardware and software used must be relevant and appropriate to the Designated Community"*. Meeting this requirement depends on clear statements and evidence about the standards in place and the level of compliance.

Another contributor stated that *"technical infrastructure provided by the repository should include at least the following: network and bandwidth, network security, office environment, machine rooms, servers, computation and storage, dedicated business, common software, etc. The repository should clarify the content of the afore-mentioned infrastructure, involving the basic configuration, operation management, backup status of key equipment, repair time and response strategies after failure, etc. [...] if outsourced they should demonstrate the technical indicators, service response, service period, responsibilities and obligations of both parties"*.

Whereas another felt that *"For TRSP whose services have been mapped to repository functions "Public transparency and clear documentation on how the two entities interact, in terms of data exchange, as well as clear roles and responsibilities, should suffice."*

Contributors emphasized that the evidence provided for R15 by either the applicant or a third-party service provider should address the following aspects

- *"reliability and stability of service*
- *service operates in accordance with the "state of the art"*
- *applicable standards and how they are met*
- *network and bandwidth, network security, office environment, machine rooms, servers, computation and storage, dedicated business, common software, etc.*
- *basic configuration of the infrastructure, operation management, backup status of key equipment, repair time and response strategies after failure, etc."*

Five contributors pointed out the usefulness of a TRSP assessment in their recommendations for R15, especially if this allows the applicant to easily reference this as evidence in their own CoreTrustSeal application. It is clear that CoreTrustSeal will need to

work with the community to define an appropriate scope and minimum expectations for 'core' technical infrastructure evidence.

One contributor pointed out that the required specifications are sufficiently described by R15. Another highlighted the importance of "*technical infrastructure (defined as external 3rd party components)*" being "exchangeable" as a repository should never be "*dependent on the specifics of a special technical infrastructure that is outsourced*".

Though the consensus was that evidence expectations should be the same for specialists, generalists, or TRSP, the broad range of recommendations around this requirement covered a scope much broader than is possible for a 'core' certification (see also R16. Security below).

Recommendations for this requirement present the strongest support for some form of assessment or certification for TRSP, but recommendations vary enough to indicate that there is no sense of 'core' expectations for practice and evidence. The CoreTrustSeal is seeking to identify the availability of technical tools and systems that support the other core requirements, not to provide a full technical certification. But note that some IT service management standards e.g. FitSM¹⁰ focus on training and standardised practice advice, not certification.

In future revisions of the Requirements, the CoreTrustSeal Board will seek to more explicitly associate the expectations of R15 with the other requirements. The CoreTrustSeal would value wider community input on agreed common minimum and ideal practices for describing technical infrastructure. This would provide consistency and comparability across repositories and their TRSP.

R16. Security

R16 Security, and to some extent R15, Technical Infrastructure, are a challenge for CoreTrustSeal as an assessment process with no direct inspection or site visit. Both topics are challenging to define and address at a 'core' level. However, the larger challenge may be the lack of community-wide agreement on minimal and ideal practice for security measures and risk mitigation (from open access, to user data, so sensitive personal datasets). How can the CoreTrustSeal best support the community definition of clearer security expectations for data, including sensitive data?

In a CoreTrustSeal review of R16 for Security, the focus is to identify whether the repository has a clear understanding of the level of security risk presented by their collections, and whether it has clear responses to those risks. This expectation would be consistent across specialist and generalist repositories.

One contributor noted that security is a moving target: "*the best you can do is ask for a clear description of what the repositories' concerns are for their data and what is their approach to meeting it*". Another suggested that security "*can be verified objectively in respect of digital security using penetration testing*". Suggestions for further guidance include a "*list of mandatory and optional requirements*" and a 'pick list' of potential security risks "*for example - fire, theft, ransomware, accidental deletion or alteration, sensitive data being accessed by*

¹⁰ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/FitSM>

the wrong people, loss of paths, loss of association of metadata and data, funding dries up, key staff leave, vendor goes bust etc.”.

Contributors pointed out a wide range of evidence to be provided by applicants, including:

- *“evidence of threat analyses and risk assessment relating to malicious actions, human error, disasters, technical failure, and organizational continuity, and how these inform the design of an efficient and scalable security system;*
- *measures to protect the infrastructure’s physical security, boundary security, system security, data security, and operation security*
- *risk assessment to inform security levels for data collections”*

The latter has particular relevance in cases where the applicant stores sensitive data, which require higher levels of security. Though this requirement is in the technical section, CoreTrustSeal is interested in the full range of factors that influence data security and the repository’s ability to demonstrate awareness and responsiveness across physical boundaries, systems, and data operations.

Contributors suggested that CoreTrustSeal should support applicants with guidance such as:

- *“a checklist of mandatory and optional requirements*
- *suggestions for the repository’s security management measures*
- *guidelines for managing a data security management plan*
- *recommendations for compliance with specific norms, conventions and legislations*
- *pointing to, or including, a list of types of security risks.”*

The recommendations make it clear that the level of security has to be determined based on the data, not based on the repository type. It is clear that not all of these areas of security can be brought within scope for a ‘core’ certification like CoreTrustSeal. There is a need to further refine the vision and scope for this requirement. One approach might be to differentiate between basic premises, systems, and data security, and to separate out any questions related to tiers of sensitive data. One contributor mentioned that an RDA working group might be a place to further discuss these questions.